

ENGLISH TEST ANXIETY LEVEL OF JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL AND ITS RELATIONSHIP TO SELF-REGULATING CAPACITY IN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

The study aimed to determine the relationship between the test anxiety level and the self-regulating capacity in language learning of Junior High School Students. A correlational research design was employed. It utilized two standardized survey questionnaires: the first was used to determine the students' level of self-regulating capacity in language learning in terms of commitment control, metacognition control, satiation control, emotion control and environment control, and the second one was to identify the level of English test anxiety of the students in terms of worry, emotionality and total anxiety. This study revealed that the participants have a high level of self-regulating capacity in language learning. Moreover, the participants' level of test anxiety is also high. Subsequently, Pearson's correlation test revealed that there is no significant relationship between the participants' various aspects of self-regulating capacity in language learning and their level of test anxiety in terms of worry and total level of anxiety. However, it was found that there is a significant relationship between self-regulating capacity in terms of commitment control, satiation control, and environment control and the level of test anxiety in terms of emotionality. On the other hand, there is no significant relationship between the other aspect of self-regulating capacity in language learning in terms of metacognition and emotion control and the level of test anxiety in terms of emotionality. Henceforth, this study recommended a policy-based modified resilience framework for learners; training for school administrators, curriculum designers, teachers, school guidance counselors, and parents; and an intervention program for a whole academic year. Thus, this would help the students sustain their self-regulating capacity in

language learning and in managing their test anxiety, leading them to be resilient and productive learners amid any challenges in school.

Keywords: *English test anxiety level, intervention program, language learning, self-regulating capacity, test anxiety*

INTRODUCTION

The student's intellectual accomplishment or academic achievement is highly valued in today's educational system. Academic achievement indicates whether students have accomplished the specified learning outcomes (Kumari, 2020). A successful academic learning outcome is essential for both students and teachers because it will test the students' understanding of the lesson and the teachers' effectiveness in teaching. Consequently, examinations are given to the students for teachers and educators to evaluate if the lesson objectives have been attained.

Pachaiappan et al. (2023) stated that exams are used to assess student learning and as a key instrument for admissions to post-secondary education and for accountability at the teacher, school, and ministry levels. Furthermore, tests hold greater importance because they serve as a basis for learning success rates. Consequently, they are given as a form of assessment to determine the student's level of understanding of a particular subject. Hence, they are essential to intervene in the factors hindering the student's examination performance.

Among the various emotions that English as a foreign language learners may experience, positive emotions have been particularly highlighted by this approach, as they can enhance learners' self-regulation, a key construct that has been recognized for its close links with emotion, behavior, and long-term academic achievement (Li et al., 2024). Yin (2020) also revealed that self-regulation affects learners' emotions and performance. This emphasizes that it is essential to condition one's emotions to enhance self-regulation.

Howard (2020) stated that test anxiety refers to unfavorable physiological, emotional, and cognitive reactions to an examination or assessment, with symptoms including rapid heart rate and breathing and worry about performing poorly, usually occurring before, during, or after an assessed performance. As cited by Liu et al. (2021), researchers have reported that between 25% and 40% of students exhibit test anxiety. Students who suffer from test anxiety go through stressful and unpleasant experiences that could harm the student's physical and mental health extensively (Pachaiappan et al., 2023). Based on this information, anxiety does not only prevent students from having better test results, but it will also affect their whole being.

Anxiety in education is a problem that needs to be resolved if not taken seriously, which can hinder productivity and lead to a decline in academic ability, learning outcomes, and even physical problems (Mukhlis et al., 2020). However, Jerrim (2022)

indicated that a very low level of anxiety may lead to poor exam performance as students do not make sufficient preparation. Therefore, it can be argued that the association between test anxiety and test results is affected by the amount of anxiety experienced. As a result of the given information, a moderate level of test anxiety may be ideal for students to be successful.

Apart from anxiety, Barber et. al (2023) stated that self-regulation is an affective factor that affects learning. The concept of self-regulation has become significant with teachers' desire to provide students with learning skills and students need to organize their learning activities. Being able to regulate and control oneself is one of the most significant human characteristics (Ozhiganova, 2018) that is connected with reflection, self-awareness, and emotional processes in achieving goals and leading to self-development and the realization of success in the learners' academic pursuit (Lather et al., 2015, as cited in Pahuriray, 2021). According to the context given, the students' learning is affected by their self-regulation capacity, which is essential for their success rate of learning.

Pahuriray (2021) stressed that self-regulation is a set of behaviors such as goal setting, time management, strategy formation for the learning process, self-evaluation, motivation, getting help, and beliefs about academic performance. Therefore, self-regulation requires learners to take active roles in their learning process.

There is a significant relationship between high test anxiety and poor study skills of students. It also stated that students who do not prepare enough for exams experience a great deal of anxiety (Pahuriray, 2021). Morosanova and Fomina (2017) suggest that students can acquire the psychological competencies to pass the exams successfully when they develop conscious self-regulation for educational activities. In this matter, it is being analyzed that self-regulation positively affects the students' test performance.

Henceforth, this study aimed to determine the participants' self-regulating capacity in language learning and evaluate whether their self-regulating capacity has a significant relationship to their test anxiety level in English. The result of this study would also serve as a basis for developing an intervention program that would help learners enhance their self-regulating capacity in language learning and manage their test anxiety in English. The findings of this study would benefit the teachers, parents, learners, researchers, and administrators.

Research Questions

This study primarily aimed to determine the students' self-regulated capacity in language learning and the level of test anxiety among Grade 7 and 8 students attending Alviola Integrated School-Annex.

Specifically, this study would like to address the following questions:

1. What is the level of self-regulated language learning capacity of the participants when taken as a whole and in terms of:

- 1.1. commitment control;
 - 1.2. metacognition control;
 - 1.3. satiation control;
 - 1.4. emotion control, and
 - 1.5. environment control?
2. What are the anxiety levels of students in English tests in terms of:
- 2.1 worry, and
 - 2.2 emotionality?
3. Is there a relationship between the students' self-regulating capacity in language learning and the level of anxiety in English tests?
4. Based on the data gathered, what intervention program may be proposed?
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METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study employed a correlational research design. McCombes (2019) stated that a correlational research design assesses a relationship between variables without manipulating the result of the study. The design utilized in this study determined the relationship between the level of self-regulated capacity in language learning and test anxiety level of 7th and 8th junior high school students in Alviola Integrated School-Annex without making any interference. The study utilized two standardized questionnaires. The first questionnaire determined the test anxiety level of the participants in terms of worry and emotionality. On the other hand, the second questionnaire identified the level of the participants' self-regulating capacity in language learning in terms of commitment, metacognition, satiation, emotion, and environment control.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in one of the public schools in Butuan City, the Alviola Integrated School-Annex. This school is located at Brgy. Baan 3 New Covered Court, Butuan City. Alviola Integrated School is part of the North District in the Division of Butuan City. It has two campuses; the main campus is located at Alviola Village, Butuan City, while the Annex school is located at Baan 3.

This school was considered the annex of Alviola National High School. Previously, this school was integrated into F.R Sibayan Elementary School, and it was only this school year – 2023-2024 when the school was relocated to its new location in New Brgy. Hall, Baan 3, Butuan City. The school is temporarily located in the evacuation center in Baan 3 due to a lack of classrooms, but new classrooms are currently under construction.

Participants of The Study

The participants of the study were the 127 Grade 7th and 8th students in Alviola Integrated School-Annex, as shown in the table below.

Table 1.
Distribution of Participants

Grade Level	Population	Sample
Grade 7	71	47
Grade 8	100	80
Total	171	127

The participants' grade levels were chosen as to the convenience of the researcher's end as the teacher of the participants.

Map of the Research Locale

Sampling Design

The sample of the study consisted of 127 students or 74 percent of the total population of grade 7 and 8 students of Alviola Integrated School-Annex. The participants were determined using a simple random sampling technique. Of the participants participating in the study, 47 were grade 7, and 80 were grade 8 students.

Research Instrument

The study used two standardized questionnaires to test the students' test anxiety levels, and the second was for self-regulating capacity in language learning.

The Test Anxiety Inventory (TAI), adapted from Spielberger (1980), was used to test the anxiety level of the students. The TAI questionnaire was composed of 20 items which used a four-point Likert scale for each item, where (1) – almost never, (2) – sometimes, (3) – often, and (4) – almost always. It contains three subscales: Test Anxiety-Total (TAI-T), Test Anxiety-Worry (TAI-W), and Test Anxiety-Emotionality (TAI-E). Eight items of the Test Anxiety Inventory measure the TAI-W (# 3,4,5,6,7,14,17, and 20), eight items measure TAI-E (# 2,8,9,10,11,15,16, and 18), and the remaining four for measuring TAI-T (# 1,12,13, and 19).

The second instrument was an adopted questionnaire from Liu (2009) to evaluate the student's Self-Regulating Capacity in Language Learning. It contained 27 questions, nine items for commitment control (# 4,7,10,12,18,21,22,24, and 26), 6 for metacognition control (# 5,9,11,14,20, and 27), 4 for satiation control (# 1,8,15, and 16), 6 for emotion control (#2,6,13,19,23, and 25) and 2 for environment control (# 3 and 17). It uses the 4-Likert scale that ranges from “disagree,” “slightly disagree,” “slightly agree,” and “agree.”

Scoring and Quantification

The level of the students' self-regulated capacity in language learning will be quantified on a 4-Likert scale that ranges from “disagree,” “slightly disagree,” “slightly agree,” and “agree.” On the other hand, the test anxiety is also a 4-Likert Scale that ranges from (1) – almost never, (2) – sometimes, (3) – often, and (4) – almost always.

Rating Scale of the Participants' Level of Self-Regulated Capacity in Language Learning

Response	Verbal Description	Range	Remark
4	Strongly Agree	3.50-4.00	Very High Level of Self-regulation
3	Agree	2.50-3.49	High Level of Self-regulation
2	Disagree	1.50-2.49	Low Level of Self-regulation
1	Strongly Disagree	1.00-1.49	Very Low Level of Self-regulation

Rating Scale of the Participants' Level of Test Anxiety

Response	Verbal Description	Range	Remark
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4	Strongly Agree	3.50-4.00	Very High Level of Test Anxiety
3	Agree	2.50-3.49	High Level of Self-regulation
2	Disagree	1.50-2.49	Low Level of Self-regulation
1	Strongly Disagree	1.00-1.49	Very Low Level of Self-regulation

Data-Gathering Procedure

The study employed the following strategies in data gathering:

Entry Protocol Phase. Before conducting the study, the researcher sent a letter of permission to the school head to survey the grade 7 and 8 students of Alviola Integrated School-Annex.

Administration and Retrieval Phase. The questionnaires were personally handed out and administered by the researcher. Before administering the questionnaires, the researcher conducted an orientation on what the research was all about; after the administration, the researcher collected the test questionnaire.

Organization Phase. The researcher gathered the participants' responses and consolidated the data.

Data Interpretation Phase. After organizing the participants' responses, the data were submitted to a statistician for data analysis.

Statistical Treatment

The study used the following statistical tool to analyze the data:

Mean. This statistical tool determines the level of anxiety and self-regulating capacity in language learning of the participants.

Pearson Correlation Coefficient. This was utilized to determine whether a significant relationship exists between the participants' self-regulatory skills and English test anxiety.

RESULTS

This chapter presents the data gathered through the research instrument used in the study. It provides presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data in graphs and tables with textual explanation.

Research Question 1. Level of Self-Regulating Capacity in Language Learning

Table 2 presents the mean distribution of the level of self-regulating capacity in language learning of the participants when taken as a whole and in terms of commitment control.

The standardized questionnaire consists of 27 questions, and to get the level of commitment control, there are nine items to answer; these items are number 10, 4, 12, 22, 24, 7, 26, 18, and 21; the rest of the items indicate the other self-regulating capacity.

Table 2 also shows the item numbers and indicators and the verbal description and interpretation of the mean. Specifically, the indicators are the questions that assess the participants' commitment control level.

Furthermore, the verbal description is based on the mean that ranges from strongly agree to strongly disagree, which is then interpreted from very high to very low level of self-regulating capacity in language learning. Additionally, the item numbers were arranged according to their mean, from highest to lowest. It started from indicator number 10th and indicator number 21st.

Table 2.

Mean distribution of the level of self-regulating capacity in language learning in terms of commitment control.

Item no.	Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
10	When learning English, I persist until I reach the goals that I make for myself.	3.30	Agree	High
4	When learning English, I have my special techniques to achieve my learning objectives	3.18	Agree	High
12	I believe I can overcome all the difficulties in English learning and achieve my English learning goals	3.14	Agree	High
22	When studying English, I know how to maintain my concentration.	2.96	Agree	High
24	When learning English, I can effectively solve the problems I encounter during the learning process.	2.94	Agree	High
7	When leaning English, I believe I can achieve my goals more quickly than expected.	2.94	Agree	High

26	When I am behind my English learning schedule; I know how to speed up my learning progress.	2.89	Agree	High
18	When I study English, I do not allow anything to interfere with my already-planned learning schedule	2.58	Agree	High
21	When I studied English in the past, I often gave up halfway during the learning process	2.47	Disagree	Low
Average		2.93	Agree	High

Ranges of Mean: 1.00-1.49-Strongly disagree, 1.50-2.49-Disagree, 2.50-3.49-Agree, 3.50-4.00-Strongly agree

As inferred from Table 2, the 10th indicator, which states that when learning English, the learners persist until they reach the goals that they make for themselves, garnered the highest weighted mean of 3.30. The participants agreed as described, and it is interpreted that they have a high self-regulating capacity in language learning in terms of commitment control.

The result shows that learners are committed and persistent in continuing to strive until their goals in learning English are accomplished. The learners know the importance of being committed and not giving up on achieving learning goals. This is also a manifestation that the learners wanted to obtain a passing score in their examinations because of their competence and commitment to learning. On the other hand, Pahuriray (2021) found that students demonstrated a low level of commitment control over the participants' language learning. This also implies that not all students are committed to learning English and reaching their goals.

The lowest garnered mean is the 21st indicator, which states that when the learners studied English in the past, they often gave up halfway through the learning process; it has a weighted mean of 2.47, which is interpreted as low. The result interpreted that the participants are committed and do not give up halfway through the learning process. Since the interpretation is low, it shows that most of the participants disagree with the idea of giving up halfway through the learning process, and it shows that the participants are serious and committed to the process of learning.

The overall mean distribution of the level of self-regulating capacity in learning English in terms of commitment control is 2.93 and is interpreted as high. This implies that the participants have high commitment control in language learning. Çelebi-Özkul (2020) found that the strength of young people and learners' commitment to the goal will affect how much they will strive to achieve the goal. Similarly, Kizilcec et al. (2017) discovered that learners with higher levels of commitment demonstrated higher levels of self-regulated learning strategies and desirable achievement. This achievement includes having desirable scores in assessments.

Next is the Table 3 which shows the mean distribution of the participants' self-regulating capacity level in language learning in terms of metacognition control. Out of 27 questions from the standardized questionnaire, six (6) questions will get the level of metacognition control; these items are numbers 5, 9, 27, 14, 11, and 20.

In addition, Table 3 presents the item numbers, indicators, and verbal description and interpretation of the mean. The indicators are the questions assessing the participants' metacognition control level.

Moreover, the verbal description is based on the mean that ranges from strongly agree to strongly disagree, which is then interpreted from very high to very low level of self-regulating capacity in language learning. As inferred from the table, the item numbers were arranged from highest to lowest mean.

Table 3.

Mean distribution of the level of self-regulating capacity in language learning in terms of metacognition control.

Item no.	Indicator	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
5	When studying English, I have my special techniques to keep my concentration focused.	3.13	Agree	High
9	When learning English, I think my methods of controlling my concentration are effective.	3.09	Agree	High
27	When studying English, I am easily distracted.	3.08	Agree	High
14	When it comes to learning English, I think my methods of controlling procrastination is effective.	2.86	Agree	High
11	When it comes to learning English, I have my special techniques to prevent procrastination.	2.76	Agree	High
20	When it comes to studying English, I tend to procrastinate the learning.	2.53	Agree	High
	Average	2.99	Agree	High

Mean: 1.00-1.49-Strongly disagree, 1.50-2.49-Disagree, 2.50-3.49-Agree, 3.50-4.00-Strongly agree

The 5th item got the highest weighted mean of 3.13, which is interpreted as high. It states that when studying English, the learners have special techniques to keep their concentration focused. This implies that they can easily understand the learning materials if they apply learning techniques. This signifies the importance of using learning techniques in learning activities because they maintain students' concentration.

On the other hand, the lowest weighted mean is the 20th item, which has a weighted mean of 2.53 and is interpreted as high. This indicator states that learners tend to procrastinate learning when it comes to studying English. Rahimi et al. (2021) state that the relationship between academic emotions and academic procrastination has been well-documented in the literature. The result implies that the learners are fond of procrastinating in their learning process. If the participants are great procrastinators, it also means that they don't pay much attention to the activities related to their learning. Rahimi et al. (2021) cited that negative emotions (anxiety) were found to trigger more academic procrastination.

The overall weighted mean of the participant's self-regulated language learning capacity level in terms of metacognition control is 2.99, which can be interpreted as high. The result concludes that the participants have a high level of metacognition control.

Drigas (2021) stated that metacognition is the ability to self-monitor, self-regulate, and adapt thoughts, emotions, and behaviors to recognize and discriminate between functional and dysfunctional mental or emotional states to know the full range of one's vital points. This implies that metacognition plays a significant role in students' self-regulation in assessment and testing. However, Cao (2007) found that metacognitive awareness may not automatically translate into self-regulatory behaviors in learning. This finding raises a series of fundamental questions about the nature and function of metacognition in learning.

For Table 4 below, it shows the mean distribution of the participants' self-regulating capacity level in language learning in terms of satiation control. A standardized questionnaire is used to test the level of satiation control of the participants, and out of 27 questions, four (4) specific questions will get the level of satiation control; these items are numbers 1, 8, 15, and 16.

Moreover, Table 4 presents the item numbers, indicators, verbal descriptions, and mean interpretation. The indicators are the questions assessing the participants' satiation control level. The overall average or mean will test the level of the participant's self-regulating capacity in language learning in terms of satiation control.

Furthermore, the verbal description is based on the scoring quantification of the mean that ranges from strongly agree to strongly disagree, which is then interpreted from very high to very low level of self-regulating capacity in language learning.

As inferred from the table 4, the item numbers were arranged from the highest to lowest mean. The item number 16th was first presented in Table 4 because it has the

highest mean. The item number 1 is placed in the last part of Table 4 because it garnered the lowest mean among the indicators in determining the mean distribution of the level of automated capacity in language learning in terms of satiation control.

Table 4.

Mean distribution of the level of self-regulating capacity in language learning in terms of satiation control.

Item no.	Questions	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
16	When feeling bored with learning English, I know how to regulate my mood to invigorate the learning process	2.97	Agree	High
15	During the process of learning English, I am confident that I can overcome any sense of boredom	2.90	Agree	High
8	I feel satisfied with the methods I use to eliminate the boredom in studying English.	2.89	Agree	High
1	Once the novelty of learning English is gone, I easily become impatient about it.	2.23	Disagree	Low
Average		2.86	Agree	High

Ranges Mean:1.00-1.49-Strongly disagree, 1.50-2.49-Disagree, 2.50-3.49-Agree, 3.50-4.00-Strongly agree

As indicated in Table 4, the 16th item got the highest weighted mean of 2.97 and is interpreted as high; this item states that when students feel bored with learning English, they know how to regulate their mood to invigorate the learning process; this shows that the learners have the strength to divert themselves in the learning process in the middle of boredom. Çepnisevcan (2021) asserted that satiation control is related to adding extra attraction to the tasks and coping with boredom; this revealed that students need to be trained in dealing with boredom while learning and studying. The result implies that when the learners feel bored during the learning process, they will find ways to regulate their boredom.

On the other hand, the 1st item got the lowest weighted mean of 2.23. The 1st item states that once the novelty of learning English is gone, the learners easily become impatient about it. Eastwood et al. (2019) noted that boredom is an unpleasant emotion; it can also signal the need to become more engaged and inspire people to seek novel sources of stimulation. Moreover, boredom can motivate students to initiate positive coping behavior; however, boredom is often linked to adverse mental health and academic outcomes (Eastwood et al., 2019). Depression, anxiety, drug or other substance addiction, and decreased quality of life are associated with frequent boredom (Chin et al., 2017). The interpretation of the participants' disagreement on impatience implies that the learners know how to eliminate boredom when learning English because it will limit their capacity to achieve academic goals and obtain passing scores in their assessments.

The overall mean for indicating the level of self-regulating capacity in language learning in terms of satiation control is 2.86, which can be interpreted as high. However, Çepni (2021) showed that the least agreed subscale of self-regulating capacity in learning was satiation control, which is about controlling boredom while studying. The descriptive statistics reveal that students must be trained to cope with boredom while learning and studying. Nevertheless, the result shows that the participants agreed to regulate themselves towards boredom.

For Table 5 below, it displays the mean distribution of the participant's level of emotion control as a self-regulating capacity in language learning. The participants' level of satiation control is assessed with a standardized questionnaire; of the 27 questions, six (6) specific questions—numbers 2, 6, 25, 23, 13, and 19—will determine the participant's level of satiation control.

Additionally, the item numbers, indicators, verbal descriptions, and mean interpretation are shown in Table 5. The questions that determine participants' degree of satiation control serve as indicators. The participant's ability to self-regulate in terms of satiation control will be assessed based on the overall mean or average.

Moreover, the verbal description relies on quantifying the mean score, which spans from strongly agree to strongly disagree. This score is understood as a level of self-regulation in language learning that is very high to very low. The item numbers were organized from highest to lowest mean, as seen from the table.

As inferred from the table 5, the item numbers were arranged from the highest to lowest mean. The item number 2 was first presented in Table 5 because it has the highest mean. The item number 19 is placed in the last part of Table 5 because it garnered the lowest mean among the indicators in determining the mean distribution of the level of automated capacity in language learning in terms of emotion control.

Table 5.

Mean distribution of the level of self-regulating capacity in language learning in terms of emotion control.

Item no.	Questions	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
2	When I feel stressed about English learning, I know how to reduce this stress.	3.09	Agree	High
6	I feel satisfied with the methods I use to reduce the stress of English learning	3.05	Agree	High
25	When learning English, I know how to manage my personal emotions to make the learning efficient	3.00	Agree	High
23	When I feel stressed about learning English, I know how to handle the stress.	2.92	Agree	High
13	When I feel stressed about learning English, I cope with this problem Immediately	2.82	Agree	High
19	When I learn English, I am easily upset by the challenge of more difficult materials.	2.69	Agree	High
	Average	2.86	Agree	High

Ranges of Mean: 1.00-1.49-Strongly disagree, 1.50-2.49-Disagree, 2.50-3.49-Agree, 3.50-4.00-Strongly agree

As described in Table 5, the second (2nd) item got the highest mean of 3.09, which states that when learners feel stressed about English learning, they know how to reduce it. The 2nd indicator is interpreted as high, and the participants agreed to the statement as described. Rudland (2019) affirmed that stress tends to be portrayed as a hindrance to learning. Hence, emotional control is significant in learning because stress will be prevented once an individual knows how to regulate their emotions. Rudland (2019) added that numerous articles in health professional education have reported “stress” with various stimuli, including deficiency of knowledge, lack of competence, patient interaction, questioning, examinations, assessments, and assignments. It implies that stress, as an example of emotion, should be taken seriously in the learning process or acquisition.

For the lowest mean, the 19th indicator garnered an average of 2.69, which states that when learners learn English, they easily get upset by the challenges of

more materials. The participants agreed to the statement, and the level was interpreted as high. Drigas (2021) indicated that regulating stress and emotions depends on cognitive skills such as attention. This implies that your emotion, like getting upset, is connected to your level of thinking; that's why thinking positively will also impact regulated emotion.

For the overall mean, the participants' emotion control is high, which obtained a mean of 2.86. The result infers that the participants handle their emotions accordingly to make learning efficient and cope with stress effectively. In some studies, it was indicated that emotions do not play a significant role in context. Pahuriray (2021) revealed that the participants' level of self-regulated language learning capacity in terms of emotion was low. The result from the previous study mentioned implies that the participants cannot cope with stress when learning English. However, the study concluded that the participants agreed with emotion control in learning and seen as effective in learning.

Following is the Table 6 which presents the average distribution of emotion control levels among participants to determine the self-regulating capacity levels in language learning. This control level is evaluated using a standardized questionnaire; precisely, two (2) questions out of 27—numbered 3 and 17—ascertain each participant's level of environment control.

Furthermore, Table 6 includes the item numbers, indicators, verbal interpretations, and average scores. The selected questions are crucial for assessing the participants' environment control levels and measuring their self-regulation capability in language learning. Environment control is one of the various aspects of self-regulating capacity in language learning.

As inferred from the table 6, the item numbers were arranged from the highest to lowest mean. The item number 3 was first presented in Table 6 because it has the highest mean. The item number 17 is placed in the last part of Table 6 because it garnered the lowest mean among the indicators in determining the mean distribution of the level of automated capacity in language learning in terms of emotion control.

In addition, the interpretation of the average scores ranges from strongly agree to strongly disagree, representing a spectrum of self-regulation ability in language learning from very high to very low. As detailed in the table, the questions are arranged from the highest to the lowest mean score.

Table 6.

Mean distribution of the level of self-regulating capacity in learning English in terms of environment control.

Item No.	Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
3	When I study English, I look for a good learning environment.	3.33	Agree	High
17	When I am studying English and the learning environment becomes unsuitable, I try to sort out the problem.	3.02	Agree	High
Average		3.41	Agree	High

Mean: 1.00-1.49-Strongly disagree, 1.50-2.49-Disagree, 2.50-3.49-Agree, 3.50-4.00-Strongly agree

As indicated in Table 6, the third (3rd) item got the highest mean of 3.33, and the environment control of the participants is interpreted as high. The third indicator states that learners who study English look for a good learning environment. Usman et al. (2019) believed a learning environment with easily accessible amenities would ensure successful teaching and learning processes and student academic accomplishment. This implies that the student's performance, retention of knowledge, and acquisition of learning are affected by their environment.

The second question, or the 17th indicator, got a weighted mean of 3.02, which can also be interpreted as high. This indicator states that when learners study English, and the learning environment becomes unsuitable, they try to sort out the problem. It relates to the understanding that a learning environment affects students' behavior and learning (Mohamad, 2021). Mohamad added that both learning and behavior are regarded as environmental responses and found that the learning environment insignificantly influences students' academic engagement.

The overall mean is 3.41, and the participants agreed that environment control contributes to their language learning process. The result revealed that the participants have a high level of environmental control. The findings are supported by Bahrami (2022), who conveyed that self-regulating strategies used by the participants in their ways significantly affect personal and environmental factors in the use of self-regulated learning strategies.

However, Tseng (2006) indicated that only the value of environment control was slightly less, whereas the other component of self-regulation measures was well within the satisfactory range. Furthermore, student participation in the learning environment is crucial to academic engagement. The result aligns with this study's theory, where the learning environment affects students' behavior and learning (Lipoff, 2018).

Research Question 2. Test Anxiety level of students in English

Table 7 shows the anxiety level of the participants in English tests in terms of worry. It includes the item numbers, questions, mean, verbal description, and interpretation. To determine the level of test anxiety among the participants, a standardized questionnaire with 20 questions was used, and in terms of worry, it was comprised of eight questions. These are item numbers 20, 4, 14, 3, 5, 7, 17, and 6. Additionally, the item numbers presented in Table 7 are arranged from highest to lowest mean with a verbal description from always almost to almost never and with an interpretation from very high to very low.

Table 7.

Mean distribution of the level of test anxiety in English in terms of worry.

Item no.	Questions	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
20	During examinations, I get so nervous that I forget facts I really know.	2.82	Often	High
4	I freeze up on important exam	2.80	Often	High
14	I seem to defeat myself while working on important tests	2.77	Often	High
3	Thinking about my grade in a course interferes with my work on tests.	2.76	Often	High
5	During exams, I find myself thinking I will get through the school	2.65	Often	High
7	Thoughts of doing poorly interfere with my concentration on tests.	2.62	Often	High
17	During tests, I find myself thinking about the consequences of failing.	2.46	Sometimes	Low
6	The harder I work at taking a test, the more confused I get.	2.40	Sometimes	Low
	Average	2.73	Often	High

Ranges of Mean: 1.00-1.49-Almost Never, 1.50-2.49-Sometimes, 2.50-3.49-Often, 3.50-4.00-Almost always

The 20th item got the highest weighted mean of 2.82, which stated that the students often get so nervous during examinations that they forget facts they know. The garnered mean can be interpreted as high and described as often. The result implies that the participants' anxiety interferes with the learners' capacity to concentrate because they are nervous, and it results in mental blocks created by anxiety. Achanan

et. al (2021) stated that anxiety, low- motivation, inhabitation, introversion, and low self-esteem can create a mental block and craft an affective filter that prevents learners' comprehensible input from acquiring competency in second language learning. This indicates that if students study for the exam, anxiety takes over, and they will forget everything they have studied because nervousness will be on their cognitive.

On the other hand, the 6th item got the lowest mean, which states that the more challenging learners work at taking a test, the more confused they get. The situation sometimes happened to the students as described, and it got a weighted mean of 2.40 and is interpreted as high. Tanner (2017) stated that if students are permitted to be confused, they are provided with the ability to think and use their metacognition. This implies that critical thinking and metacognition work if a learner is confused.

The overall weighted mean is 2.73, or the learners "often" worry about their examinations and tests. This implies that the learners are almost always concerned about the result and often feel nervous and freeze up. In this context, the learners show concern for the outcome and consequences of their actions and emotions, and their anxiety starts with the worry they possess. However, several studies justify that the issue of test anxiety is not a significant determinant of students' adverse learning outcomes (Brady et al., 2018).

Table 8 shows the mean distribution of anxiety levels of students in English tests in terms of emotionality. It includes the item numbers, questions, verbal description, and interpretation. It consists of 7 questions out of 20 items from the standardized questionnaire; the item numbers are 10, 2, 8, 11, 18, 9, 15, and 16.

Table 8.

Mean distribution of the level of anxiety in learning English in terms of emotionality

Item no.	Indicators	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
10	I start feeling very uneasy just before getting a test paper back.	2.89	Often	High
2	While taking examinations, I have an uneasy, upset feeling.	2.79	Often	High
8	I feel very jittery when taking an important test.	2.77	Often	High

11	During tests, I feel very tense.	2.72	Often	High
18	I feel my heart beating very fast during important tests.	2.70	Often	High
9	Even when I am well prepared for a test, I feel very nervous	2.69	Often	High
15	I feel very panicky when I take an important test.	2.69	Often	High
16	I worry a great deal before taking an important examination.	2.69	Often	High
	Average	2.80	Often	High

Ranges of Mean: 1.00-1.49-Almost Never, 1.50-2.49-Sometimes, 2.50-3.49-Often, 3.50-4.00-Almost always

The highest weighted mean is the 10th item, which states that the learners start feeling uncomfortable and uneasy just before getting a test paperback. This item got a weighted mean of 2.89, described as “often” and interpreted as high. This implies that the learner is often not confident and anxious to answer the test given to them. Kumari (2014) asserted that the signs of stress before and during examination are irregular sleep, feelings of tiredness, isolation or sadness, aches all over, suffering from stomach upset, feeling restlessness, or leading to a condition where they cannot recall whatever they studied. It is experienced by many participants in managing their test anxiety and dealing with emotions.

The lowest weighted mean is 2.69, the indicator for the 15th and 16th. The 15th indicator states that the learners feel panicky when taking an important test, while the 16th indicates that learners worry a lot before taking a critical examination. Both indicators are described as “often” and interpreted as high. The result revealed that the participants often panic and get worried during their examination, which results in a high level of test anxiety. Tang (2024) focused on the single aspect of physical or psychological symptom burden while ignoring their interaction. This implies that anxiety does not only focus on the emotion of an individual, but it also includes physical disturbances such as shaky hands and upset stomach. However, most studies suggest that though anxiety could have an impact on a student, it may not necessarily be the sole reason for the poor learning outcomes of learners (Brady et al., 2018).

For the overall result, the weighted average is 2.80, which indicates that the participants are often affected by their emotions during their tests and learning process.

The result shows that the participants have a high level of test anxiety in terms of emotionality.

Next is Table 9 which shows students' mean distribution of anxiety levels in English tests in terms of Total Anxiety. It includes the item numbers, questions, mean, verbal description, and interpretation. The questions from the standardized questionnaire that will determine the level of total anxiety comprise four (4) questions out of 20; these item numbers are 12, 13, 19, and 1.

Table 9.
Mean distribution of the level of test anxiety in learning English in terms of total anxiety.

Item No.	Indicator	Mean	Verbal Description	Interpretation
12	I wish examinations did not bother me so much.	2.77	Often	High
13	During important tests, I am so tense that my stomach gets upset.	2.62	Often	High
19	After an exam is over, I try to stop worrying about it, but I just can't.	2.49	Sometimes	Low
1	I feel confident and relaxed while taking tests.	2.48	Sometimes	Low
Average		2.69	Often	High

Mean: 1.00-1.49-Almost Never, 1.50-2.49-Sometimes, 2.50-3.49-Often, 3.50-4.00-Almost always

The weighted mean of the highest item is 2.77, the 12th indicator, which states that learners wish that examinations did not bother them so much. It is described that the learner-participants “often” feel this way. This implies that the learners are bothered with their exams – physically and emotionally. However, numerous studies also suggested that anxiety may be required to ensure that learners take teaching and learning seriously (Brady et al., 2018). This implies that moderate anxiety also has positive effects on the part of the student’s learning.

The indicator with the lowest weighted mean is the first, with a weighted mean of 2.48. This indicator states that the learners “sometimes” feel confident while taking the test. The result revealed that the participants have low confidence and feel more anxious answering a test. However, Kisac et al. (2013) stated that people with higher self-confidence in their capabilities approach complicated tasks as challenges to be mastered and found that the level of self-confidence of the students about learning is adequate in their cognition skills.

The overall mean revealed that the participants had a high level of total test anxiety. It has a weighted average of 2.69, implying that the participants often feel anxious, have low confidence, and cannot stop worrying even if the exam is over.

Research Question 3.1 Significant Relationship between learners' Self-Regulated Capacity in Language Learning and the Level of Test Anxiety

Table 10 shows the significant relationship between the students' self-regulating capacity in language learning and the level of test anxiety in English in terms of worry. The table includes the computation of Pearson r , p -value and remark.

Table 10.

Significant relationship between the students' self-regulating capacity in language learning and the level of anxiety in English test in terms of worry.

Students' self-regulating capacity in language learning	Pearson r	p-value	Remark
Commitment control	0.059	0.518	Not Significant
Metacognition control	-0.012	0.895	Not Significant
Satiation control	0.106	0.243	Not Significant
Emotion Control	-0.025	0.780	Not Significant
Environment control	0.012	0.891	Not Significant

**Tested at 0.05 level of significance using Pearson's r correlation.*

As shown in Table 10, it can be noted that the relationship between the students' self-regulating capacity in language learning and the level of anxiety in English tests in terms of worry is not significant at $\alpha=0.05$. The relationship of both metacognition control and emotion control are negative, with $r = -0.012$ and $r = -0.025$, respectively. It can also be noted that commitment control, satiation control, and environmental control have no significant relationship with test anxiety in terms of worry $\alpha=0.05$ since the computed p -values are 0.518, 0.243, and 0.891.

The results suggest that the anxiety or worry of the participants in their test and how they regulate themselves in language learning do not have a strong correlation. The insignificance in all various aspects of self-regulating capacity in language learning may indicate that these aspects are not the primary variable for self-regulating capacity in a language learning context. In other words, the findings from the study imply that commitment, metacognition, satiation, emotion, and environment control may not be the primary determinants of the participants' level of test anxiety.

Overall, the results emphasized the complexity of the relationship between the self-regulating capacity in language learning and the test anxiety of the participants. This needs further research to understand the possible mechanism that will contribute to exploring additional ideas that will support the implication of self-regulation and the management of test anxiety. Such insight will significantly contribute to developing better intervention programs for test anxiety and self-regulating capacity in language learning.

Research Question 3.2 Significant relationship between learners' self-regulated capacity in language learning and the level of test anxiety in terms of emotionality.

Table 11 shows the significant relationship between the students' self-regulating capacity in language learning and the level of anxiety in English test in terms of emotionality. The table includes the computation of Pearson r , p -value and remark. The level of significance is tested by 0.05 using Pearson's r correlation.

Table 11.

Significant relationship between the students' self-regulating capacity in language learning and the level of anxiety in English test in terms of emotionality.

Students' self-regulating capacity in language learning	Pearson r	p-value	Remark
Commitment control	0.178	0.048	Significant
Metacognition control	0.112	0.214	Not Significant
Satiation control	0.195	0.030	Significant
Emotion Control	-0.019	0.834	Not Significant
Environment control	0.170	0.040	Significant

****tested at 0.05 level of significance using Pearson's r correlation***

Based on the projected data, emotion control has a negative relationship and is insignificant at $\alpha=0.05$, with a p -value of 0.834. Similarly, metacognition control also shows no significance with a p -value of 0.214. On the other hand, commitment control, satiation control, and environment control have a significant relationship with anxiety in terms of emotionally, with a p -value of 0.048, 0.030, and 0.040, respectively. This means that the consistency and environment correlate with the level of anxiety that you have in terms of emotions.

Pahuriray (2021) stated that one of the key conclusions drawn from the findings is that self-regulated language learning capacity significantly impacts students. This suggests that having a self-controlled language learning capacity aids scholastic success in English. Finally, it is concluded that the students' self-regulated language learning capacity is a critical factor to consider in improving their academic achievement in English. This implies that if the learners apply self-regulation in learning, they will also perform better in assessments and be less likely to have test anxiety.

The result also implies that commitment, satiation, and environment control have an essential role in managing the test anxiety levels of the students. The positive correlation in commitment, satiation, and environment control indicates the participants' higher level of self-regulating capacity in language learning. The findings also indicate that the participants with commitment towards their language learning, experience less satiation, and have control over their learning environment may still experience test anxiety. The pressure to perform well on tests increases test anxiety among students who are committed to their learning process and always look for a good learning environment. Regarding satiation control, the students who are satisfied with their learning progress

may also experience test anxiety because of the recognized necessity to improve continuously.

Research Question 3.3 Significant relationship between learners’ self-regulated capacity in language learning and the test anxiety in terms of total anxiety.

Table 12 shows the relationship between the students self-regulating capacity in language learning and their test anxiety in terms of total anxiety. The tables include the computation of Pearson *r*, *p*-value and remark. The level of significance is tested by 0.05 using Pearson’s *r* correlation.

Table 12.

Significant relationship between the students’ self-regulating capacity in language learning and the total anxiety in English test.

Students’ self-regulating capacity in language learning	Pearson <i>r</i>	<i>p</i>-value	Remark
Commitment control	0.057	0.527	Not Significant
Metacognition control	0.025	0.786	Not Significant
Satiation control	-0.023	0.804	Not Significant
Emotion Control	0.010	0.911	Not Significant
Environment control	0.070	0.438	Not Significant

**tested at 0.05 level of significance using Pearson’s *r* correlation*

The findings in Table 12 show that the correlation between the participants’ self-regulating capacity in language learning and their total anxiety level in the English test reveals no significance in all various aspects of self-regulating capacity in language learning. The significance level was tested at 0.05 using Pearson’s *r* correlation, and none of the self-regulating capacities in language learning showed statistically significant correlations in total anxiety. The result implies that the participants’ ability to regulate themselves in language learning is not directly linked to the level of their total anxiety in English tests.

Moreover, the insignificant correlation between the self-regulating capacity in language learning and the total anxiety of the participants is relatively independent in the context of assessment based on the results. Additionally, the test anxiety of the participants may also be influenced by other factors beyond the students’ self-regulating capacity. These could include the pressure during the test, the fear of failure, the test format, and their language proficiency level, which are not directly related to the participants’ self-regulating capacity.

Additionally, the lack of correlations between the self-regulating capacity of language learning and test anxiety in terms of total anxiety may be moderated by other variables and individual differences that were not identified in the study. Future research could further explore the understanding between the students’ self-regulating capacity and test anxiety in the learning context.

Research Question 4. Intervention Program for Self-Regulating Capacity and Test Anxiety Level of the Students

The matrix below shows the school-based Self-Regulation and Anxiety Intervention Program for Alviola Integrated School-Annex. This intervention program is entitled “Peer Support Circle: Managing Test Anxiety and Developing Self-Regulating Capacity in Language Learning. This will help students manage their test anxiety and sustain their self-regulating capacity.

Proposed School-Based Self-Regulation and Anxiety Intervention Program

- I. Program Title : Peer Support Circle: Managing Test Anxiety and Developing Self-Regulating Capacity in Language Learning
- II. Program Description : This intervention program is designed based on the findings of the study. This intervention program aims to develop the students’ self-regulating capacity and assess their test anxiety in English language learning.
- III. Date and Venue : Alviola Integrate School - Annex
- IV. DepEd Activity : Integration of Peer Support Initiatives Program to help students practice self-regulation skills in test anxiety
- V. Target Participants : Students experiencing high-level test anxiety related to English Language Learning.
- VI. Project Leaders : School Head, Guidance counselor, Class Advisers and researcher

VII. Rationale:

There are already existing groups and clubs in schools, such as Glee clubs, Dance troupes, and many more, but this peer support circle will create an environment that supports every student with their school work and emotional needs.

In this group, the learners can share their experiences and difficulties in their studies. They will receive mutual encouragement and materials from their peers and teachers to manage their test anxiety.

Moreover, the students will also be provided with training and materials that will support the objectives of this program.

VIII. Objectives:

This intervention program aims to:

- to provide the learners with a safe place to express their concerns and seek advice for their studies and life in general;
- to encourage understanding among the students who are also facing the same challenges;
- to facilitate peer discussion with the learners on strategies for coping with test anxiety and,
- to support students with their psychological and emotional needs in learning English.
- to maintain the level of self-regulating capacity of the students and
- to provide learners with instructional materials and training to support them in managing their test anxiety and self-regulating capacity in language learning.

IX. Preparatory of Activity/Pre-work:

- A faculty Meeting will be held to inform the teachers of the proposed intervention program.
- Club meetings will also be conducted to let the students join the intervention program.

X. Activity Implementation Flow:

- There will be a designation for members and committees for the intervention program. It is composed of a head, facilitators, and members.
- There will be guided discussion for the committee to lead the proper flow of the intervention program.

XI. Documentation/Report In-charge:

- Teacher In-Charge
- Club President/Secretary

XII. Requirements:

- Minutes of the meeting
- Memorandum for the proper conduct of peer group for an intervention program, signed by school head and class advisers.

XIII. Means of Verification/Monitoring and Evaluation Mechanics:

- Duly signed Memorandum of Understanding
- Attendance and Pictures

Phases of Proposed Scheme

Phase I. Pre-Intervention Phase						
Time Frame	Program	Strategies/Activities	Objectives	Facilitators/Implementors	Budget	Means of Verification
Week1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Endorsement of the designed intervention program to the School Head of Alviola Integrated School - Annex. Make a memorandum for conducting the intervention program. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conduct a faculty meeting and endorse the designed intervention program to the School Head and teachers of Alviola Integrated School – Annex. Let the school head sign the school memorandum for the intervention program. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To inform the school head and the teachers with the intervention program. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> School head and non-teaching staff Researcher Teachers 	None	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attendance Pictures Signed Memorandum by the School head and researcher

Phase II. During Intervention Phase						
Time Frame	Program	Strategies/Activities	Objectives	Facilitators/Implementors	Budget	Means of Verification
Week 2	Assessment and Goal Setting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The researcher will let the students answer a questionnaire (Pre-Assessment) that will identify the students' level of test anxiety in English language and self-regulation skills. Guide the participants with the intervention process, the researcher will introduce and set a specific, measurable, achievable, relevant, and time-bound (SMART) goals. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To assess the anxiety levels of the student's self-regulation skills among the students of Alviola Integrated School-Annex by implementing a questionnaire to accurately assess its level. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Guidance Counselor of the School Invited Keynote Speaker expert in the field of self-regulation and anxiety Teachers Students 	₱1,000	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attendance form Accomplishment Report Certificates Compiled Result of Assessment answered by the students

Phase II. During Intervention Phase						
Time Frame	Program	Strategies/Activities	Objectives	Facilitators/Implementors	Budget	Means of Verification
Week 3-4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Psycho-education 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The participants from Alviola Integrated School-Annex will be educated with the nature of test anxiety and its effects on their performance in school. Additionally, they will also be educated about importance of self-regulation strategies. • The participants will also be provided with information about common self-regulation techniques such as cognitive restructuring, deep breathing and mindfulness. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To enhance the participants' self-regulating capacity and lessen their test anxiety. • To teach the participants with the knowledge and techniques about test anxiety and self-regulation techniques, enable to address and alleviate test anxiety and enhance the overall performance of the participants. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Guidance Counselor of the School • Invited Keynote Speaker expert in the field of self-regulation and anxiety • Teachers • Students 	₱ 1,000	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attendance form • Accomplishment Report (The content of the accomplishment report includes the activity conducted during the week, its objectives and introduction. This also includes the success indicator of the activity conducted.)

Phase II. During Intervention Phase						
Time Frame	Program	Strategies/Activities	Objectives	Facilitators/Implementors	Budget	Means of Verification
Week 5-6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cognitive Restructuring and Coping Strategies for Test Anxiety 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thought Record Sheet • The participants will keep a thought record sheet where they will write down their anxious thoughts related to tests and exams. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To identify specific thought triggers that impact emotional state during testing situations. • To identify anxious thoughts related to test and manage test anxiety proactively. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Invited Keynote Speaker expert in the field of self-regulation and anxiety. • Language Teachers • Students 	None	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attendance Form • Checklist completed by participants to evaluate their progress in self-regulation capacity and managing test anxiety

Phase II. During Intervention Phase						
Time Frame	Program	Strategies/ Activities	Objectives	Facilitators/ Implementors	Budget	Means of Verification
Week 7	Stress Management and Time-Optimization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Visualization and Positive Affirmations • Mindful breathing exercise and Muscle Relaxation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To guide and encourage the participants to successfully prepare themselves through visualization • To promote relaxation and reduce anxiety before and during stressful situations like taking exams. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • English Teachers 	None	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Attendance • Accomplishment Report

Phase II. During Intervention Phase						
Time Frame	Program	Strategies/ Activities	Objectives	Facilitators/ Implementors	Budget	Means of Verification
Week 8	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Building Supportive Networks and Resources • Progress Monitoring 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish Peer Support Group • Discuss changes and improvement with the participants self-regulation and test anxiety. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To foster a sense of belongingness to the participants where they can come together to share experiences. • To evaluate the process of the participants in terms of managing test anxiety and self-regulating skills. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-teaching Staff • Teachers 	None	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluation Form • Learning Plans • Assessments

Phase III Post-Intervention Phase						
Time Frame	Program	Strategies/Activities	Objectives	Facilitators/Implementors	Budget	Means of Verification
Week 9	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Program Evaluation and Continuous Improvement • Implement School-based policy for Peer-Support Activity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Post Assessment to identify the changes in the participants level of test anxiety and self-regulation. • Regular monitoring of the participants' progress. • Gather feedback from the participants to identify the areas for improvement. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • To identify the areas of improvement in terms of test anxiety and self-regulation capacity. • To gather feedback and ensure the effectiveness of the intervention program. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-teaching Staff • Researcher • Teachers 	None	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Performance Assessment • Attendance record • Observation Logs

DISCUSSION

The study aimed to determine the self-regulating capacity of language learners and their test anxiety in English. The self-regulating capacity of language learning focused on the commitment control, environment control, satiation control, metacognition control and emotion control. For test anxiety level, the level was tested in terms of worry and emotionality.

Additionally, it employed correlational research to identify the relationship between self-regulating capacity in language learning and test anxiety. It utilized two standardized survey questionnaires: the first was used to determine the students' level of self-regulating capacity in language learning in terms of commitment control, metacognition control, satiation control, emotion control, and environment control, and the second one was to identify the level of English test anxiety of the students in terms of worry, emotionality and total fear.

The analysis revealed that the students demonstrated high levels in various aspects of self-regulating capacity and environment control, indicating the highest level. Moreover, the evidence from the data also showed high levels of anxiety, particularly concerning worry, emotionality, and total anxiety. Furthermore, it underscores the pressing need for effective interventions and support mechanisms to address mental health concerns in the participants.

The result revealed that there is no significant relationship between the student's level of test anxiety in terms of worry and total level of anxiety and their self-regulating capacity in language learning in all aspects. However, in terms of emotionality, there is a significant relationship in terms of commitment, satiation, and environment control. The result concludes that how worried students feel about tests and their total level of anxiety don't seem to affect how well they can regulate or control themselves when learning a language. Additionally, the findings suggest that emotionality significantly influences commitment, satiation, and environment control

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn.

The study revealed that the level of self-regulating capacity in learning English in terms of commitment control, metacognition control, satiation control, emotion control, and environment control is high. Similarly, the level of test anxiety of the participants in terms of worry, emotionality, and total anxiety is also high.

For the correlation between self-regulating capacity in language learning and test anxiety, the study found no significant relationship between the students' self-regulating capacity in language learning and the level of test anxiety in English tests in terms of worry. It was also evident that there is no significant relationship between self-regulating capacity in terms of metacognition and emotion control and the level of test anxiety in English in terms of emotionality. However, the study found a significant relationship between the self-regulating capacity in language learning in terms of commitment, satiation, and environment control and test anxiety in terms of emotionality. Additionally, based on the analysis, there is no significant relationship between the students' self-regulation capacity and the total anxiety level of students. Thus, the research proposed an intervention program that would help maintain the student's self-regulating capacity in language learning and manage their test anxiety in English.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations are drawn:

1. The school may consider incorporating a school-based policy on peer-tutoring activity to improve the student's performance in terms of self-regulating capacity in language learning assessment.
2. Teachers may integrate self-regulating capacity in language learning and assessment in their teaching practices.
3. The Department of Education Supervisors and subject coordinators may be encouraged to design training related to improving the mental health of both teachers and students in separate sessions.

4. Teachers and administrators may create a budget proposal for well-modified, reviewed, and approved instructional materials per quarter for assessment and language learning.
5. The school and administrator may mold future teachers or researchers to help build an active and credible research culture with a poll of research experts.
6. Other researchers may consider the use of qualitative research related to identifying the test anxiety level of other senior high school and college level students.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The present study adhered to the informed consent before the participants' participation; they were informed about the purpose and implication of the study, and they were assured of their freedom to withdraw from participating without any consequences. For anonymity assurance, the researchers ensured that the confidentiality of the participant's responses was observed. Throughout the study, the participants' comfort was given priority. The authors also affirmed that during the study, no conflict of interest existed that influenced the study's interpretation. Strict measures were also implemented to prevent plagiarism in all parts of the study. The findings were interpreted with no biases. Lastly, the data were not manipulated for other purposes but for research purposes.

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